

STIFFNESS OF SHORT-FIBRE-REINFORCED MATERIALS:
MODEL AND ITS COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL DATA

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ABSTRACT

The current model for predicting the longitudinal modulus of composites containing discontinuous reinforcement is discussed with respect to the features specific to short fibres: presence of fibre ends, distribution $n(L)$ with respect to their length L , and distribution $o(\theta)$ due to the fibre orientation θ . The inability of the model to predict either the transverse modulus or the modulus in any off-axis direction is remedied by a) introducing analytical expressions quantifying the effects of polydispersity in L and θ , b) coupling the two distributions via assumption that the fibre length controls the variance of $o(\theta)$, and c) deriving an expression which manifests 'conservation of the reinforcing potential'.

Experimental data found in the literature are simulated using the material characteristics of the constituents, experimental variables and a minimum of rational, adjustable parameters.

Comparison of the theoretical output with the experimental data reveals satisfactory agreement, with 92 % of the simulations carried out (65 in total) falling within ± 30 % relative error.

INTRODUCTION

The current model for predicting stiffness of composites containing short fibres is based on generalisation of additivity rules that govern the longitudinal and transverse moduli of the laminae [1, 2], and more specifically on the relationships derived by Cox [3], Darlington [4] and Kelly [5]. For uniaxially aligned fibres of a given length L , the longitudinal modulus W_0 is derived as:

$$W_0 = V_f E_f \mu_L + (1 - V_f) E_m, \quad (1)$$

where E_f and E_m are the elastic moduli of the fibre and the matrix, V_f is the volume fraction of reinforcement and μ_L is a length correction factor given [3] by:

$$\mu_L = 1 - \frac{\tanh(\beta L/2)}{\beta L/2}, \quad (2)$$

where β stands for:

$$\beta = \left[\frac{2G_m}{E_f r_0^2 \ln(R/r_0)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (3)$$

Here G_m is the shear modulus of the matrix related to E_m via the Poisson ratio ν_m of the matrix $G_m = E_m/[2(1 + \nu_m)]$, r_0 the radius of the cylindrical reinforcement and R/r_0 a reinforcement displacement factor which can be related to the reinforcement loading V_f :

$$R/r_0 \sim 1.84 V_f^{-\frac{1}{2}} . \quad (4)$$

We also account for a slight reduction in the stiffness due to fibre discontinuity in the other principal direction and write for the transverse modulus W_{90} :

$$1/W_{90} = V_f/(\mu_L E_f) + (1 - V_f)/E_m . \quad (5)$$

Composite processing routes are often associated with an energy input high enough to cause fibre fracture and alignment, resulting in the reinforcement being polydisperse with respect to fibre length and orientation. Defining $n(L_i)$ as the number of fibres of the length L_i and h as the total number of fractions different in length, Darlington [4] accounted for the fibre length distribution by summing the contributions of the individual fractions to the factor μ_L :

$$\mu_L = \frac{1}{V_f} \sum_{i=1}^h \mu_{L_i} n(L_i) , \quad (6)$$

where μ_{L_i} is given by Equation (2) after substitution for L_i .

As to the polydispersity in orientation, the perfect alignment $\theta = 0$ is defined to coincide with the principal direction $\psi = 0$ and different degrees of misalignment are accounted for [6] by introducing the orientation factor μ_a , defined as:

$$\mu_a = \sum_{i=1}^H 0(\theta_i) \cos^4 \theta_i , \quad (7)$$

where H is the total number of fractions considered and $0(\theta_i)$ is the normalised fibre fraction of species oriented at angle θ_i in the plane of the distribution. The final expression for the longitudinal modulus Z_0 of the composite reinforced with short, misaligned fibres polydisperse in their length is [4]:

$$Z_0 = V_f E_f \mu_L \mu_a + (1 - V_f) E_m . \quad (8)$$

Globally, Equations (1)-(8) represent the current state of modelling of the stiffness of short-fibre-reinforced composites.

MODEL EXTENSION

The current model appears to be deficient in four areas:

- i. It does not formulate the way to derive the transverse modulus Z_{90} of a composite reinforced with short, misaligned fibres of different lengths.

- ii. Although it quantifies the detrimental effect of misaligned fibres on the modulus Z_0 , it does not account for their incremental effect towards Z_{90} , i.e. the model does not reflect 'conservation of the reinforcing potential' of a certain loading of short fibres. (Note that $\theta_i = 90$ results in $\mu_a = 0$, implying $Z_0 < E_m$.)
- iii. It requires the distribution functions with respect to the fibre length $n(L)$ and their distribution $0(\theta)$ to be known explicitly.
- iv. Unavailability of Z_{90} prevents macromechanical derivation of the stiffness in any arbitrary direction ψ .

As point iii seems to be the least problematic we address it here by dealing with the distribution in the length first and that involving orientations later.

By referring to the statistics on polymers we assume that the fibre length distribution is described by a function resembling that used for expressing molecular weight distribution. All the major types of distributions have been considered as possible candidates, but it is the Schulz-Zimm type that is proposed. This was prompted by the ease of its generation, its relative flexibility and, finally, by a successful fit of experimental data [7]. The Schulz-Zimm distribution [8] may be generated as:

$$n(L) = L^{k-1} \exp\{-k/\bar{L}_n\}L, \quad (9)$$

or, more conveniently, in its normalised form:

$$N(L_i) = n(L_i) / \sum_{i=1}^h n(L_i), \quad (10)$$

with \bar{L}_n being the first moment of the distribution $n(L)$ and k the parameter ($k > 1$) defined by means of \bar{L}_n and the second moment:

$$(k + 1)/k = \bar{L}_w / \bar{L}_n. \quad (11)$$

Concerning the distribution $0(\theta)$ with respect to the fibre orientation we assume the fibres to be misaligned symmetrically with respect to the most abundant orientation occurring at $\theta = 0^\circ$, i.e. in that principal direction associated with the maximum composite stiffness (flow direction during composite manufacturing). The Gaussian distribution in the form:

$$g(\theta) = \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2} \frac{\theta^2}{\sigma_\theta^2}\right\}, \quad (12)$$

is used in its normalised form:

$$G(\theta_i) = g(\theta_i) / \sum_{i=1}^H g(\theta_i) \quad (13)$$

to redistribute a given fraction containing species of the length L over the interval $-90 \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$ by means of

$$o(\theta_j, L_i) = N(L_i) G(\theta_j), \quad (14)$$

and the final distribution of orientations is obtained by summation of contributions from all species varying in length:

$$O(\theta_j) = \sum_{i=1}^h o(\theta_j, L_i) . \quad (15)$$

As the longer fibres are likely to be more prone to orientation than the shorter ones we have coupled the $N(L)$ and $o(\theta)$ distributions by postulating that the absolute fibre length L controls the variance σ_θ as follows:

For very short fibres ($L < L'$), the composite manufacturing process is assumed not to induce any orientation, thus:

$$O(\theta) = N(L)/H . \quad (16)$$

For the intermediate length $L' < L < L''$ region, which represents a substantial part of the $N(L)$ distribution, the variance is assumed to be a linear decreasing function of L in the form:

$$\sigma_\theta = A(L - L'')/(L' - L'') , \quad (17)$$

where A is the variance of the Gaussian distribution of the species having the length L' . Finally, a provision is made for the longest fibres, which, however, represent only an insignificant portion of the $N(L)$ to be aligned perfectly, i.e.

$$o(0, L_i) = N(L_i) . \quad (18)$$

Concerning the 'conservation of the reinforcing potential' (point ii above) the following analysis introduces the problem. If the fibres are completely misaligned (to be understood as 100 % oriented in the direction $\theta = 90^\circ$) there must be a switch-over between the engineering constants, i.e. the maximum modulus is to be exhibited at $\psi = 90^\circ$, which means that Z_{90} represents the longitudinal modulus of this hypothetical composite. At the same time, Z_0 becomes the transverse modulus. For any intermediate state, fibre misalignment causes reduction in Z_0 and an increase in Z_{90} . If the material is isotropic (i.e. all fibre orientations are equally probable), $O(\theta_i) = 1/H$, then Z_0 must be identical to Z_{90} .

In order to accommodate these interrelationships between the moduli we base our approach on the macromechanical modelling of the off-axis composite stiffness and define the orientation factor as:

$$\langle \mu_\psi \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^H \mu(\psi - \theta_i) O(\theta_i) , \quad (19)$$

with

$$\mu(\psi - \theta_i) = \frac{W(\psi - \theta_i) - W_{90}}{W_0 - W_{90}} , \quad (20)$$

where

$$W^{-1}(\psi - \theta_i) = \frac{\cos^4(\psi - \theta_i)}{W_o} + \frac{\sin^4(\psi - \theta_i)}{W_{90}} + (1/\bar{G} - 2\bar{\nu}/W_o) [\sin(\psi - \theta_i) \cos(\psi - \theta_i)]^2 . \quad (21)$$

The shear coupling term in Equation (21) is derived by calculating the composite shear modulus \bar{G} from the Halpin-Tsai semi-empirical approach [9] and using the additivity rule for enumerating the composite Poisson ratio $\bar{\nu}$.

Executing Equations (19)-(21) twice, first for $\psi = 0$ and then for $\psi = 90$, one obtains the orientation factors $\langle \mu_o \rangle$ and $\langle \mu_{90} \rangle$, which allow the principal elastic moduli to be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} Z_o &= \langle \mu_o \rangle (W_o - W_{90}) + W_{90} \\ Z_{90} &= \langle \mu_{90} \rangle (W_o - W_{90}) + W_{90} . \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Equations (19)-(22) not only meet the objective ii but also allow the Z_{90} transverse modulus to be derived, thereby dealing with i.

Finally (objective iv), the angular dependence of the modulus Z_ψ within the interval $0 < \psi < 90^\circ$ is readily generated as:

$$Z_\psi^{-1} = \frac{\cos^4 \psi}{Z_o} + \left(\frac{1}{\bar{G}} - \frac{2\bar{\nu}}{Z_o} \right) \left(\frac{\sin 2\psi}{2} \right)^2 + \frac{\sin^4 \psi}{Z_{90}} . \quad (23)$$

PROGRAM FORMULATION

Having established the theoretical background for predicting stiffness Z_ψ of a composite reinforced with short fibres polydisperse both in their length and misalignment, it is now opportune to recall the miscellaneous magnitudes encountered so far and to map them according to their nature. These are:

- experimental variables - V_f , \bar{L}_n and ψ ,
- constituent characteristics - E_f , E_m , ν_f , ν_m and r_o ,
- adjustable parameters - k , A , L' and L'' .

They constitute the input for the computer program written in BASIC compatible with its execution on the IBM Personal Computer.

EXPERIMENTAL

A literature search was carried out for a wide range of stiffness values stemming from different combinations of the matrix/reinforcement pairs. The type of experimental information sought was a) Z_o dependence on V_f for fixed values of \bar{L}_n , b) Z_o dependence on \bar{L}_n with the parameter V_f and c) the angular dependence Z_ψ on the angle at which the specimens had been tested.

Three sets of experimental data were found covering both the thermo-plastic/thermosetting matrix representatives and the two most fundamental reinforcement types, carbon and glass fibres. These are:

Set I: Moduli of polyamide 66 reinforced ($0.067 \leq V_f \leq 0.218$) with carbon fibres ($0.04 < L_n < 0.15$ mm) and measured for $0 \leq \psi \leq 90^\circ$ as reported by Stolze [10], the composite having been prepared by injection moulding.

Set II: Angular dependence of the stiffness Z_ψ for $0 \leq \psi \leq 90^\circ$ measured by Kacir et al. [11] for epoxy (EPON 828 + curing agent Z) reinforced with $V_f = 0.5$ glass fibres of the length $3.2 \leq L_0 \leq 12.7$ mm. The composites were manufactured by the "flow moulding technique" [12].

Set III: Data from Sanadi and Piggott [13] obtained for carbon-fibre ($0.5 \leq L_0 \leq 5$ mm) reinforced ($0.20 \leq V_f \leq 0.35$) epoxy resin (EPON 815 + Ancamine 1482) in the form of Z_0 dependences on the fibre loading and the reinforcement length. A similar manufacturing procedure to that described by Kacir above was used and the composite was characterised for the distribution in fibre length and orientation. The distribution function $N(L)$ is reported to have consisted of two parts: unbroken fibres of starting length L_0 and the overall abundance w , with the portion $(1 - w)$ being distributed evenly over all the fibres having been broken during the manufacturing step; thus $N(L) = (1 - w)/(h - 1)$. The portion w appears to increase with decreasing L_0 . Further, Sanadi's structural study indicates that the fibre misalignment is symmetrical round $\theta = 0^\circ$, and that the width of $O(\theta)$ falls with increasing L_0 and is associated typically with the variance of 15° for unbroken fibres of $L_0 > 1$ mm. The structural information obtained by Sanadi played an important part in the development of the present model.

COMPARISON BETWEEN THEORY AND EXPERIMENT

This section, though of fundamental importance, is very brief: Table 1 documents all the input necessary for executing computations, while the simulated data (the continuous curves) are compared with the experiments (shown as discrete data points) in Figures 1-5. Only a few words of explanation are necessary.

- For Set I, the lower threshold was defined as $L' = 0.04$ mm owing to the composite realised (see Figure 2) with the shortest fibres being essentially isotropic. The upper value L'' coincides with the maximum length L_0 present where $N(L_0) \rightarrow 0$.
- For Set II, the model predicts the reinforcing power to be independent of the maximum (original) fibre length L_0 , i.e. the feature also vindicated by the experimental data at $\psi = 0$ and 90° . The lowest possible value $L' = 0$ was used, and L'' and A were taken as being identical to L'' and A for Set III because of the similarity in the composite manufacturing route.
- Including now also Set III, definition of $L' = 0$ and $L'' = 1.33 L_0$ in conjunction with $A = 60$ facilitates a smooth changeover from a wide distribution for very short species to $\sigma_\theta = 15^\circ$ for $L = L_0$ as observed experimentally.

Figures 1-5. Simulation of experimental sets I (Figs. 1 and 2), II (Fig. 3) and III (Figs. 4 and 5) with the input given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Summary of the input information

Set	Constituent characteristics					(Adjustable) parameters					Variables
	Fibre			Matrix		N(L) defined by		O(θ) controlled by			
	E_f	ν_f	$r_o \times 10^3$	E_m	ν_m			L'	L''	A	
I	230 [15]	0.28 [16]	4 [17]	4.5 [14]	0.35 [14]	\bar{L}_n	$k = 5$	0.04	L_o	45	$\bar{L}_n, \nu_f,$ ψ
II	72 [18]	0.20 [19]	5 [11]	7.0 (+) [19]	0.35 [19]	L_o	$w = 0.65$	0	$\frac{4}{3} L_o$	60	L_o, ψ
III	380 [20]	0.17 [20]	5 [20]	2.4 [13]	0.35 [19]	L_o	w	0	$\frac{4}{3} L_o$	60	$L_o, w,$ ν_f

Moduli expressed in GPa; \bar{L} , L', L'' and r_o in mm; ψ and A in degrees

+) derived from the transverse exper. modulus.

*) assumed.

CONCLUSIONS

The problem of predicting stiffness of composites reinforced with short fibres has been addressed by:

- surveying the current theoretical approach to modelling the tensile moduli of materials of this class;
- identifying areas of weakness in the model and extending the model, thereby bringing it closer to reality. This has been achieved by i) postulating the reinforcement to be polydisperse with respect to the fibre length L and the fibre orientation, ii) deriving an algorithm that reflects the conservation potential of the short-fibre reinforcement and iii) assuming that the absolute fibre length controls the variance of distribution in orientations;
- examining the literature and tracing three sets of experimental data on composites varying in matrix/fibre combinations, fibre length and reinforcement loading;
- simulating the experimental data, with the constituent characteristics, experimental variables and a minimum of rational, adjustable parameters all serving as input to the computer program created.

Comparison of the model output with the experimental data, shown in Figure 6, indicates that a satisfactory agreement has been achieved. Five different values for the adjustable parameters k, L', L'' and A are seen to allow 92 % of data points out of a total of 65 to be predicted to within an accuracy of ± 30 %.

Figure 6. Theory/experiment correlation

REFERENCES

1. Tsai, S.W. and Hahn, H.T., Transformation of stress and strain; Off-axis stiffness of unidirectional composites. In Introduction to Composite Materials, Technomic Publ. Co., Inc., Westport, USA, 1980, Chapters 2 (pp. 31-64) and 3 (pp. 65-113).
2. Jones, R.M., Macromechanical behaviour of a lamina. In Mechanics of Composite Materials, Scripta Book Co., Washington D.C., 1975, Chapter 2, pp. 31-84.
3. Cox, H.L., The elasticity and strength of paper and other fibrous materials. Brit. J. Appl. Phys. 1952, 3, 72-79.
4. Darlington, M.W. and Christie, M.A., Time-dependent properties of injection-moulded composites. In The Role of the Polymeric Matrix in the Processing and Structural Properties of Composite Materials, eds. J.C. Seferis and L. Nicolais, Plenum Press, London, 1971, pp. 319-355.
5. Kelly, A. and Tyson, W.R., Tensile properties of fibre-reinforced metals: Copper/tungsten and copper/molybdenum. J. Mech. Phys. Solids, 1965, 13, 329-350.
6. Krechnel, A., Fibre Reinforcement, Akademisk Verlag, Copenhagen, 1964.
7. Pennington, D., Ph.D. Thesis, University of Liverpool, 1979.
8. Peebles, L.H., Jr., Some general distribution functions and their properties. In Molecular Weight Distributions in Polymers, Interscience Publishers, London, 1971, pp. 1-47.
9. Halpin, J.C. and Kardos, J.L., The Halpin-Tsai equations: A review. Polym. Eng. & Sci., 1976, 16, 344-352.

10. Stolze, R., Chopped-carbon-fibre-reinforced thermoplastics. In Proceedings of Short-Fibre-Reinforced Thermoplastics Internat. Conf., Brunel University, UK, June 17-18th, 1985, paper II.
11. Kacir, L., Narkis, M. and Ishai, O., Aligned short-glass-fibre/epoxy composites. Composites, 1978, 89-92.
12. Kacir, L., Narkis, M. and Ishai, O., Oriented short-glass-fibre composites. I. Preparation and statistical analysis of aligned fibre mats. Polym. Eng. & Sci. 1975, 15, 525-531.
13. Sanadi, A.R. and Piggott, M.R., Interfacial effects in carbon-epoxies. I: Strength and modulus with short aligned fibres. J. Mater. Sci., 1985, 20, 421-430.
14. Brandrup, J. and Immergut, E.H., Eds., Polymer Handbook, 2nd edition, John Wiley & Sons, London, 1975, p. V-83.
15. Ref. 1, Table 9.1: Typical fibre properties, p. 380.
16. Bieling, U., Ermittlung mechanischer und thermischer Eigenschaften Kohlenstoffaserverstärkter Kunststoffe, Thesis IKV Aachen, 1983, p. 32.
17. Bader, M.G. In The Technology of Fibre-Reinforced Composite Materials, course organised by University of Surrey (July 1985), Volume II, Lecture 6, p. 6.
18. Holmes, M. and Just, D.J., GRP in Structural Engineering, Applied Science Publishers, London, 1983, p. 29.
19. Ref. 1, p. 399.
20. Kelly, A. and Mileiko, S.T., Eds., Fabrication of Composites. Handbook of Composites, Vol. 4, North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1983, p. 114.